

Selective Anchoring Groups for Molecular Electronic Junctions with ITO Electrodes

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ABSTRACT:

Indium tin oxide (ITO) is an attractive substrate for single-molecule electronics since it is transparent while maintaining electrical conductivity. Although it has been used before as a contacting electrode in single-molecule electrical studies, these studies have been limited to the use of carboxylic acid terminal groups for binding molecular wires to the ITO substrates. There is thus the need to investigate other anchoring groups with potential for binding effectively to ITO. With this aim, we have investigated the single-molecule conductance of a series of eight tolane or "tolane-like" molecular wires with a variety of surface binding groups. We first used gold-molecule-gold junctions to identify promising targets for ITO selectivity. We then assessed the propensity and selectivity of carboxylic acid, cyanoacrylic acid, and pyridinium-squarate to bind to ITO and promote the formation of molecular heterojunctions. We found that pyridinium squarate zwitterions display excellent selectivity for binding to ITO over gold surfaces, with contact resistivity comparable to that of carboxylic acids. These single-molecule experiments are complemented by surface chemical characterization with X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, quartz crystal microbalance, contact angle determination, and nanolithography using an atomic force microscope. Finally, we report the first density-functional theory calculations involving ITO electrodes to model charge transport through ITO-molecule-gold heterojunctions.

In 2007, Nongjian Tao and coauthors presented an inspiring work on the use of indium tin oxide (ITO) as a contacting electrode in single molecular electronics,¹ also highlighting its potentially attractive features in such studies. These include its optical transparency while maintaining good electrical conductivity, which is a result of the high electron doping provided by tin. Although ITO, which is an n-type degenerate semiconductor with an optical bandgap of 3.5-4.3 eV,^{2,3} had been widely used for many years in photovoltaic devices and organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs), this study by Tao and co-workers¹ was the first to demonstrate that ITO can be used to form single-molecule electrical junctions.¹ It was shown that n-alkane backbones terminated with carboxylic acid anchoring groups at each end could form molecular bridges between an ITO surface and an ITO-coated tip of a conducting atomic force microscope (c-AFM). This approach enabled defined single-molecule electrical measurements with ITO contacting electrodes using a homologous series of n-alkane dioic acids (with $n = 2, 4, \text{ and } 6$) as molecular targets. The authors demonstrated that stable junctions could be formed, although the ITO-carboxylate binding was found to be around 7-8 times weaker than the widely deployed thiol-gold anchoring.¹

The contact conductance for ITO-carboxylate was also discovered to be less than that for gold-carboxylate contacts, although not by a large margin (425 versus 477 nS). This pioneering work by Tao and co-workers paved the way for ITO as a contacting electrode in single-molecule electronics and eventually, a demonstration of single-molecule optoelectronics.

Tao and co-workers also highlighted the potential advantage of ITO over conventional metal contacting electrodes such as gold,¹ since the latter quench photoexcited molecular states, opening up the possibility to deploy ITO contacting electrodes in single-molecule optoelectronic and photovoltaic devices. Although Tao did not explore this aspect in this 2007 publication, a later study by the Lindsay group did indeed use ITO as a contacting electrode in single-molecule optoelec-

tronic measurements.⁴ They used the same carboxylate/carboxylic acid attachment chemistry as Tao and co-workers¹ to anchor a photoactive fullerene-porphyrin dyad to the ITO surface.⁴ A scanning tunneling microscope (STM) was used to contact the top of the fullerene-porphyrin dyad molecule, thereby forming ITO-fullerene/porphyrin-gold heterojunctions, with a pyridyl group anchoring to the gold STM tip. Upon illumination, through the transparent ITO, the junction conductance increased considerably, which was attributed to the formation of long-lived charge-separated states between the molecular dyad and ITO surface.⁴ ITO has also been used as a material to form electrical contacts to molecular films from mesoscopic to macroscopic areas. For example, Atesci et al. have contacted self-assembled monolayers of ruthenium complexes on ITO with ITO coated c-AFM probes and phosphonic acid anchoring group (~ 100 molecules contacted)⁵ and studied the rectifying properties of the resulting junctions.

Beyond the two publications mentioned above,^{1,4} to the best of our knowledge, there appears to have been no further development of ITO as a contacting electrode for forming *single-molecule* electrical junctions. This lack of development is perhaps surprising given the continued interest in ITO and other transparent conductive electrodes in photovoltaic and OLED devices. In addition, within the field of molecular electronics, there has also been a continued interest in the optical modulation of electrical devices. This interest is also complemented by using ITO as a gate material in high-performance CMOS transistors, where it has been deployed in channel thickness down to 1 nm.⁶ It is noteworthy that ITO has featured strongly in sensor and electrochemical applications, so electron transfer at ITO-molecule interfaces (see, e.g., the work performed by Gooding et al.⁷) is a theme of continuing contemporary attention. These collected interest areas for ITO highlight the further need to develop it as a contacting electrode in nanoscale electronic junctions or fundamental studies of electron transport at ITO-molecule interfaces. This is the subject of the present work, which examines several new anchoring groups for binding to ITO for the formation of nanoscale electronic junctions.⁵

Although there has been substantial work on developing large-area molecular monolayers on ITO,^{8,13} for example, phosphonic acids and amino silanes, in the case of single-molecule electrical junctions to ITO, the interface chemistry has not been extended beyond carboxylic acids. In this present study, nonsymmetric tolane or "tolane-like" molecular wires with novel surface binding groups are used to form molecular junctions between an ITO surface and a gold tip. An STM is used to monitor the stochastic formation of these ITO-molecule-gold heterojunctions by measuring telegraphic tunneling current signals with the so-called current-time (*I-t*) technique.^{14,15} Binding to the top gold electrode is favorably achieved through gold-sulfur linkages. Surface characterization is performed with X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), quartz crystal microbalance, contact angle measurements, and atomic force microscopy nanolithographic carving. These collective results highlight that pyridinium squarate is a favorable new group for selectively forming contacts to ITO. The study concludes with the presentation of new theoretical modeling of single-molecule electrical junctions with ITO contacting electrodes, which is challenging given the chemical and physical heterogeneity of such substrates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Current-Distance Screening Using Gold Substrates.

One of the key aspects we considered for choosing the anchoring groups is their ability to selectively bind to transparent electrodes such as ITO. This section describes our initial screening of new anchoring groups using gold substrates before we move onto ITO substrates in following sections. Here, in this first part, we used the STM break-junction (STM-BJ) technique¹⁶ to assess the conductance of a set of molecular wires and their behavior in gold-molecule-gold junctions. For this, we screen a variety of molecular wires all containing a tolane (diphenylacetylene) or "tolane-like" backbone, which is a well-studied archetypal molecular wire.^{17,19} Our envisioned experimental measurement procedures, described in following sections, entails molecules selectively bound to an ITO substrate through one anchoring group and contacted by a gold STM tip to complete the ITO-molecule-gold molecular junction. The successful molecules therefore require distinct anchoring groups that allow for selective binding to ITO at one end and the gold STM tip at the other. To assess the selectivity of binding groups to gold, the initial screening was carried out for compounds shown in Figure 1 using the STM-BJ method on gold substrates. Should the binding groups proposed for ITO contacting electrodes also give rise to the formation of good gold-molecule-gold junctions there would be little chance of selective binding in the subsequent ITO-molecule-gold junctions.

As described above, each of the molecular wires has on one side a well-studied sulfur anchoring group for binding to gold and on the other with an anchoring group designed for ITO. Figure 1 presents the workflow used in this project, with the structures (top), the 2D conductance histograms from the screening experiments with gold-molecule-gold homojunctions (middle panel) and then a summary of the detailed investigations made to identify the most favorable ITO surface binding (lower panel). The first two wires are dimethyldihydrobenzo[b]thiophene-tolane-carboxylic acid (**1**) and methylthio-tolane-3-pentanedione (**2**). A representative 2D conductance-distance plot of **1** shows that this molecular wire readily forms molecular junctions between two gold electrodes, and the same applies to **2**. This result indicates that the oxygen-containing anchoring groups in **1** and **2** interact with gold, since they form good junctions and therefore, they would not have any selectivity toward ITO.

The next three wires are dimethylbenzothiophene-tolane-pyridinium-squarate (**3**), dimethylbenzothiophene-tolane-3-pentanedione (**4**), and (*Z*)-3-(4-((4-(methylthio)phenyl)ethynyl)phenyl)-4-oxopent-2-en-2-olate which contains a (*Z*)-4-oxobut-2-en-2-olate binding group (**5**). Inspiration for the pyridinium squarate group was drawn from Li et al.²⁰ For these squarate compounds in this study, the molecular backbone cannot strictly be called a "tolane" as they have a pyridinium ring in place of one of the phenyls, and hence, they are referred to here as "tolane-like" (since like tolanes they have two aromatic rings connected by an acetylene linker). This group of wires shows potential for achieving controlled-orientation in heterojunctions. However, as **2** readily forms junctions between two gold electrodes and keto-enol tautomerism can complicate the surface chemistry at a metal oxide interface, either (*Z*)-4-oxo-pent-2-en-2-olate (in **2** or **4**) or (*Z*)-4-oxobut-2-en-2-olate (in **5**) can be seen as a less suitable anchoring group for ITO. Compounds **1**, **3**, and **4**

Figure 1. Workflow scheme for the project. Molecular structures (top) are divided into three groups based on results using gold-molecule-gold homojunctions. A representative 2D conductance-distance plot from each group (middle panel) highlights differences in binding to gold electrodes. The molecular wires in group C were studied further using surface characterization experiments, current-time spectroscopy, and theoretical modeling (compounds 6-8).

possess the 3,3-dimethyl-2,3-dihydrobenzo[b]thiophene (DMBT) surface binding group which has been shown as a very effective anchor for gold break junctions.²¹ Although this would be very good for our single-molecule experiments, it is less suited for surface characterization, on account of the bulky nature of the DMBT group which might impede self-assembly and defined molecular orientation on metallic surfaces.

The final set of wires are thio-tolane-carboxylic acid (**6-carboxylate**), thio-tolane-cyanoacrylic acid (**7-acrylate**), and thio-tolane-pyridinium-squarate (**8-squarate**), shown on the right of **Figure 1** (top). In the case of **7-acrylate**, the term "acrylate" is used as an abbreviation for "cyanoacrylate". These three compounds all have a thiol functionality (protected as thioacetate) at one terminus, which is an excellent and well-studied gold surface binding group.²²⁻²⁶ All three of these wires do not readily form junctions between gold electrodes as

evidenced by the 2D histograms, an example of which is shown for **8-squarate** in **Figure 1** (middle panel, right). This behavior indicates that they are worthy of further investigation as candidates that might selectively orient in ITO-molecule-gold heterojunctions. Furthermore, the presence of a strong, covalent anchor such as a thiolate ensures robust self-assembly, advantageous for XPS experiments and surface characterization. These three molecular wires were therefore carried forward for further investigation.

Surface Characterization. Surface characterization has been achieved with X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) and contact angle measurements. In addition, nanolithographic carving of a monolayer of molecules was performed using atomic force microscopy (AFM).

A detailed description of the XPS data for compounds **6-carboxylate**, **7-acrylate**, and **8-squarate** with gold and ITO substrates is given in the **Supporting Information** (SI). Examination of XPS data for the sulfur 2p region is informative in assessing the assembly of the compounds onto ITO and in analyzing the relative propensities of the terminal groups to bind to either gold or ITO substrates. Illustrative XPS data for the sulfur 2p region for **8-squarate** is shown in **Figure 2**. XPS

Figure 2. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy data shows the lack of interaction between gold and the squarate group. XPS spectra in the S 2p region for **8-squarate** (A) in powder, (B) adsorbed onto a gold surface, and (C) adsorbed onto an ITO surface.

characterization of self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) of **8-squarate** shows that, upon self-assembly on a gold substrate, the S 2p peaks are shifted to lower binding energy, as the molecule binds covalently to the gold surface. In the case of SAMs adsorbed onto gold substrates, the ratios between unbound and bound sulfur are 35:65 for **6-carboxylate**, 52:48 for **7-acrylate**, and 16:84 for **8-squarate**. From the XPS analysis of surface bound sulfur versus sulfur not bound to the surface (see the SI), we conclude that molecules in a SAM of **8-squarate** interact with the gold substrate predominantly via the thiol group, thereby implying relatively little gold surface binding through the pyridinium squarate group. However, the same compound self-assembled on ITO shows no change in

Figure 3. Individual traces for ITO-molecule-gold junctions show current jumps, confirming the stochastic formation of single-molecule junctions. (A) Schematic setup for the current-time spectroscopy experiment with compound **6-carboxylate** as an example. (B) STM image showing the clean ITO surface. (C-E) Example traces showing jumps at the *average* current of all traces in each data set. (F-H) Example traces showing jumps at *higher* current values, which occur less frequently. Traces are offset for clarity, and all measurements were carried out using a negative sample bias of 100 mV.

binding energy in the sulfur 2p region from that of the "free" molecule (measured as powder). These results highlight the nonselectivity of (substituted) carboxylic acids over thiols for binding to gold substrates. **8-squarate**, on the other hand, displayed excellent selectivity toward ITO surfaces, since 8-squarate predominantly binds to gold through its thiol terminus.

XPS spectra have also been recorded for **8-squarate** in the N 1s region. Both a SAM of **8-squarate** on ITO and the powder sample give a pair of peaks in the N 1s region with similar peak energy values. This result indicates that the N atom in **8-squarate** has a similar binding environment for both the powder sample and the SAM on ITO. Therefore, it can be concluded that the N atom of the pyridinium moiety and the ITO substrate do not interact, and the adsorption on ITO occurs through the squarate. However, it is hard to extract information from the O 1s region of the XPS spectra, as it is a convolution of signals associated with the molecular wire with those arising from the high oxygen content of the substrate. Further details on the XPS measurements are presented in the [SL](#).

We then performed quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) measurements on a "tolane-like" compound with a squarate terminal group and no thiol anchoring group (9 in [Figure 1](#)). A QCM resonator was incubated in a 10^{-4} M solution of 9 in THF:chloroform (1:4), and the frequency was monitored as a function of time. After 48 h of incubation, no change in the frequency was observed, confirming the poor affinity of the pyridinium squarate group to a gold substrate.

Water contact angle measurements were carried out on gold and ITO substrates modified with **6-carboxylate**, **7-acrylate**, and **8-squarate** to confirm the specific affinity of the carboxylic acid, cyanoacrylic acid, and pyridinium squarate to the ITO substrate. When ITO substrates were used to support the monolayers, angles of ca. 80° were obtained in all cases. This result indicates that all three of these monolayers expose the same terminal group (i.e., the thiol/thioacetate) pointing away

from the ITO substrate. Meanwhile, for modified gold substrates supporting the monolayer, the angle values decrease to 70° , 72° , and 63° for **6-carboxylate**, **7-acrylate**, and **8-squarate**, respectively. This finding reveals that the more hydrophilic nonsulfur groups are exposed on the top surface of the film, which agrees with the conclusions from the XPS data.

Finally, we performed nanolithographic carving of a monolayer of **6-carboxylate** on ITO using an AFM contact-mode. When we scan the surface using a high force set point, we observe a carved patch on the surface (see [Figure S33](#) in the SI for details). No such change can be observed for a clean ITO substrate without a molecular layer.

Current-Time Spectroscopy Using ITO Substrates.

The *STM-I(t)* technique was used in this study, also referred to as "blinking."^{14, 15, 27-31} This method relies on stochastic binding events where molecules bind and unbind from the STM tip due to thermal fluctuations, resulting in switching between low and high current values. When the current is followed in the time domain, it has the appearance of telegraphic noise, and the technique of following the current (*I*) with time (*t*) has been therefore termed the *I(t)* method.^{14, 15} The technique can be deployed with ordered or disordered molecular monolayers or even on a sub-monolayer of molecules adsorbed on a substrate.^{14, 15} This method is suitable for our study since well-ordered molecular monolayers are not a prerequisite. Nevertheless, junction formation requires adsorption of the target molecules on ITO, which has been confirmed by the surface characterization data discussed in the preceding section. The target molecules (**6-carboxylate**, **7-acrylate**, and **8-squarate**) were adsorbed onto the ITO substrate, which was then approached using a gold STM tip ([Figure 3A](#)). As the tip is brought within sufficient distance and the STM feedback loop is turned off, abrupt changes (jumps) in the current signal indicate the stochastic formation and rupture of molecular bridges. The current signal is recorded as a function of time. Examples of such current jumps are presented in [Figure 3C-E](#), where the abrupt

increase in current corresponds to a molecular binding event, and a decrease corresponds to a molecular junction breaking event. Most of the jumps occur at relatively consistent values just below 1 nA, but all three systems occasionally show higher current jumps, as shown in Figure 3F-H. We believe these jumps at higher currents arise from molecules that coordinate to the ITO surface with a different configuration (see also the theoretical discussion below). We observed no characteristic current jumps on clean ITO substrates in the absence of molecules.

Traces comprising hundreds of individual "jumps" were compiled into conductance histograms. One-dimensional histograms were compiled from the raw traces and provide counts for the most probable average conductance values of these junctions (Figure 4A-C). The raw traces were further

Figure 4. Histograms built from the single traces show that average junction conductance values and temporal stability is comparable for all three molecules. (A-C) One-dimensional conductance histograms for **6-carboxylate** in blue (207.5 s total), **7-acrylate** in gray (97 s total), and **8-squarate** in red (173.5 s total). (D-F) Two-dimensional conductance histograms for **6-carboxylate** in blue (1863 jumps out of 3106 slices), **7-acrylate** in gray (807 jumps out of 1615 slices), and **8-squarate** in red (1266 jumps out of 2559 slices). All measurements were carried out using a negative sample bias of 100 mV. 1D histograms and 2D heat maps are normalized to the total number of seconds and jumps, respectively.

analyzed using an automated Python algorithm,^{32,33} where each trace was sliced between jumps using the second derivative of the current signal. These slices were compiled in 2D density maps (Figure 4D-F), providing insight into the temporal stability of the molecular heterojunctions. Since these 2D maps only contain the current jumps, there is no observed background as is the case for the 1D histograms. Details about data collection and analysis are provided in the [Supporting Information](#). Overall, the average junction conductance values are 7.1 nS for **6-carboxylate**, 4.6 nS for **7-acrylate**, and 5.6 nS for **8-squarate** (Figure 4A-C). Temporal stability plots (Figure 4D-F) show that the junctions with pyridinium squarate also show the greatest longevity with junctions persisting for up to ~ 100 ms under our measurement conditions.

Charge Transport Calculations. Transport calculations for junctions that involve ITO electrodes are challenging due to the complexity of the crystal lattice. We started by modeling

the ITO electrode, using an indium oxide cubic lattice substituting cationic sites with Sn using an Sn/In ratio of 0.16.^{34,37} We then used density functional theory to find an optimized structure of ITO on the gold (see methods). Next, we placed the molecules between ITO and gold electrodes and then find the optimized geometry and ground-state Hamiltonian and overlap matrix elements using the SIESTA³⁸ implementation of DFT. These results were then combined with the Gollum³⁹ implementation of the nonequilibrium Green's function method⁴⁰ to compute the transmission coefficient of the systems (see further details in the SI). To find a suitable configuration for the formation of junctions with an ITO electrode, two different bonding structures including **COO-** and **COOH** (H-bonding) on metal oxide surfaces were investigated, as shown in Figure S34 in the SI. The DFT results show that the **COO-** structure has a higher binding energy (as shown in Table SI). Figure SA illustrates an example that has a

Figure 5. Calculated transmission plots of the ITO-molecule-gold junctions compare well with the experimental results. (A) Relaxed structure of **8-squarate** between gold and ITO (see the SI for the relaxed structures of all the systems). (B) Calculated electrical conductance curves versus electrode energy.

fully relaxed geometry of the molecular structure in the junction with **8-squarate** anchoring to ITO. Our calculations indicate that **8-squarate** interacts with ITO through hydrogen bonding and electrostatic interactions (see Figure S39).

Figure SB shows the electrical conductance values of the molecules **6-carboxylate**, **7-acrylate**, and **8-square** for configurations shown in Figure S3S. Typically, the Fermi energy, E_F , lies near the middle of the HOMO-LUMO gap, and comparing with the experimental trend our results suggest that E_F falls within the highlighted region in the figure. The

calculation with three different binding configurations to electrodes for each molecule (Figures S36 and S37) indicates that electron transport through the junctions varies according to the different configurations. However, the overall trend for the average conductance over these different configurations (6-carboxylate > 8-squarate > 7-acrylate) is the same as that which we found in our experiments. This shows that, in spite of the complexity of incorporating the doped oxide semiconductor, our calculations are in good agreement with experiment.

CONCLUSIONS

We have measured electrical transport properties of a series of tolane or "tolane-like" wires using STM techniques to form metal-molecule-metal junctions. The conductance of these molecular wires with different surface binding groups was first screened using gold pair homojunctions (gold substrates and gold STM tips, respectively) and the break-junction technique. All these molecular wires have different binding group combinations on their respective termini. Single-molecule conductance values were around $10^{-3.5} G_0$ for all wires that formed junctions, which is slightly lower than values for tolane wires which have identical anchoring groups on their respective ends.¹⁷ Crucially, the pyridinium squarate group does not form junctions using only gold electrodes, making it a promising candidate as a selective ITO binding group. Bearing in mind these findings for gold-molecule-gold homojunctions, we then turned to ITO-molecule-gold heterojunctions, choosing the thiol anchoring group as a favorable gold binding group for the top contact to the gold STM tip. Here, we have shown the controlled orientation of the molecules by the design of their electrode-specific anchoring groups, which is confirmed by surface characterization experiments. The heterojunctions formed using current-time spectroscopy have reproducible conductance values. The selective binding of 8-squarate to an ITO surface offers perspectives for studies where controlled orientation is required in heterojunctions. Possible directions might include future work with junction illumination through the transparent ITO electrode contacts. Further development could include ITO-molecule-ITO homo junctions employing pyridinium squarate surface anchoring and ITO-coated STM tips.

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Author Contributions

R.J.D., A.B., and R.J.N. designed the project in consultation with other team members. I.J.P. carried out all STM experiments. A.V. supervised/provided training on the STM. I.J.P. and A.V. analyzed all the conductance data. S.M. and P.C. carried out and analyzed all surface characterization experiments. A.D., S.S., and H.S. performed all theoretical calculations in consultation with C.J.L. R.J.D. synthesized and characterized all compounds in consultation with A.B. Contributions to the manuscript writing: introduction and discussion of STM and conductance data and general discussion (I.J.P. and R.J.N.), synthesis (R.J.D.), theory (S.S.), XPS and surface characterization (S.M.), with further contributions in editing from C.J.L., A.V., S.J.H. and P.C. All authors have approved submission.

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■ DEDICATION

This article is dedicated to the memory of Professor Nongjian Tao.

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